

NOTES

The Dissociation Constants of Four Disubstituted Cinnamic Acids

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The dissociation constants of four dimethoxy substituted cinnamic acids were determined by standard spectrophotometric methods¹. For each acid the absorptivity was measured at eight wave lengths for seven concentrations in the range, 1.00×10^{-5} M to 1.00×10^{-4} M, in each of three solutions: 0.1M HCl; acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer solutions with a pH near the pK of the acid as estimated by preliminary experiments; and 0.01 M NaOH. The low solubility of the 2,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid required that its pK be evaluated without an absolute determination of its concentration. All measurements were made with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The pH values were measured with a Beckman Zeromatic pH meter. The temperature of the solutions was maintained at $25.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$. The solutions were kept in the dark, inasmuch as the compounds appeared to be unstable upon exposure to sunlight. The acids were used as supplied by K and K Laboratories, New York, without additional purification. The appearance of isobestic points in the spectra provided evidence for the purity of the compounds. The apparent pK was calculated at each concentration, assuming the activity coefficient of the undissociated acid to be unity, and employing the Davies-Robinson modification of the Debye-Hückel equation to estimate the activity coefficient of the anion². These values were then extrapolated to a bulk concentration of zero to obtain the thermodynamic dissociation constant.

The values obtained were:

Compound	pK
trans-2,3-dimethoxycinnamic acid	4.37 ± 0.03
trans- β -2,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid	4.80 ± 0.03
trans-3,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid	4.53 ± 0.03
trans-3,5-dimethoxycinnamic acid	4.36 ± 0.03

Comparison of the above values with the corresponding values for the monosubstituted methoxycinnamic acids is instructive (pKs for parent compound and the ortho-, meta- and para-methoxy-substituted compounds are, respectively, 4.44, 4.40, 4.38, and 4.54³).

1. Sager, E.E., and Siewers, I. J., *J. Research Natl. Bur. Standards*, 1950, 45, 489.
2. Robinson, R.A., in Hamer, W. J., "The Structure of Electrolytic Solutions", John Wiley & Sons Inc., New York 1959, p. 253.
3. Dippy, J. F. J., *Chem. Rev.*, 1939, 25, 151.

In 2,3-dimethoxycinnamic acid the inductive effect apparently predominates. Adjacent groups seemingly hinder, through steric effects, the mesomeric effects assignable to the ortho substituent. In 2,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid both methoxy groups, one in the ortho and one in the para-position, give rise to the electromeric effect with consequent decrease in the dissociation constant. As for 3,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid, the mesomeric effect resulting from the para-methoxy group is apparently more important than the inductive effect, since 3,4-dimethoxycinnamic acid is a weaker acid than cinnamic acid. Finally it appears that the inductive effect predominates in the case of 3,5-dimethoxycinnamic acid.

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